

Education Quarterly Reviews

Çelikpazu, E. E. (2022). The Skills of Turkish Teacher Candidates to Use the Functions of Language in the Narrative Texts. *Education Quarterly Reviews*, 5(2), 102-116.

ISSN 2621-5799

DOI: 10.31014/aior.1993.05.02.472

The online version of this article can be found at:
<https://www.asianinstituteofresearch.org/>

Published by:
The Asian Institute of Research

The *Education Quarterly Reviews* is an Open Access publication. It may be read, copied, and distributed free of charge according to the conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

The Asian Institute of Research *Education Quarterly Reviews* is a peer-reviewed International Journal. The journal covers scholarly articles in the fields of education, linguistics, literature, educational theory, research, and methodologies, curriculum, elementary and secondary education, higher education, foreign language education, teaching and learning, teacher education, education of special groups, and other fields of study related to education. As the journal is Open Access, it ensures high visibility and the increase of citations for all research articles published. The *Education Quarterly Reviews* aims to facilitate scholarly work on recent theoretical and practical aspects of education.

ASIAN INSTITUTE OF RESEARCH
Connecting Scholars Worldwide

The Skills of Turkish Teacher Candidates to Use the Functions of Language in the Narrative Texts

Esra Ekinci Çelikpazu¹

¹ Faculty of Education, Department of Turkish and Social Sciences, Recep Tayyip Erdoğan University, Rize, Turkey

Correspondence: Esra Ekinci Çelikpazu, Faculty of Education, Department of Turkish and Social Sciences, Recep Tayyip Erdoğan University, Rize, Turkey. E-mail: esra.ekinci@erdogan.edu.tr

Abstract

Communication is an important part of our life. The realization of the communication and the achievement of its purpose is possible by understanding the function of the linguistic units used by the speaker or the text producer. In this case, the communication functions of the language, which is an important part of communication, must be known/recognised. Linguists, sociologists, and psychologists have taken different approaches to classify the functions of language. One of these approaches is the classification made by Roman Jakobson from the Prague linguistics school. Jakobson considers exchanging information between addresser and addressee as an essential element in communication. He also states that language has six functions: expressiveness, referent, call, relationship, metalanguage function and artistic function. In this research, the narrative texts of Turkish teacher candidates were examined in terms of the functions of the language by using Jakobson's approach. The model of the research is case study as it covers both the collection of field-based data, and the process is related to evaluations. Data were collected through documents during the process. The documents of the research are the narrative texts prepared by the 2nd year Turkish Language Teaching students studying at a state university within the scope of the linguistics course. The results of the study showed that there is a significant difference between the pre-service teachers' use of language functions in the narrative texts they wrote before learning Roman Jakobson's classification of language functions and the narrative texts they wrote after learning.

Keywords: Turkish Education, Functions of Language, Teacher Candidates

1. Introduction

1.1 Introduce the Problem

Communication constitutes vital part of our life. It is an undeniable fact that the role of language in the communication process, which carries the real world into the borders of the fictional world, by means of signs that are a part of its magical system.

Communication is to influence the people we live with through certain signs, for a certain purpose; while trying to make this impact, it is to ensure that the other party can realize a reason worth being influenced. Therefore, the basis of communication is the sense of activating the receiver by influencing it. This purpose can only be achieved with a properly selected and formatted function.

The realization of the communication and the achievement of its purpose is possible by understanding the function of the linguistic units used by the speaker or the text producer. Communication is to influence the people we live with, through certain signs, for a certain purpose; while trying to make this impact, it is to ensure that the other party can realize a reason worth being influenced. (Keller, 1994'ten akt. Yücel, 2009: 515) Therefore, the basis of communication is the feeling of activating by influencing the receiver. This purpose can only be achieved with a properly selected and formatted function. The realization of the communication and the achievement of its purpose is possible by understanding the function of the linguistic units used by the speaker or the text producer. In this case, the communication functions of the language, which is an important part of communication, must be known/recognised.

Although it is thought that the most important function of language is to communicate between people and / or societies, the main function of language before communication is "to establish a relationship between human and object and transfer the real world to the fictional world". (Börekcı, 2009) People feel the need to produce and concretize messages only as they begin to make sense of the real world/world of objects/environment and establish relationships. This need is also the basis of the use of language, which can be described as the act of being conscious of its existence and conveying this consciousness to others. Language use is the result of the process of recognizing, recognizing, establishing relationships, forming thoughts, and sharing one's thoughts, and is a part of linguistic communication. In other words, the use of language is an indicator of the attitude that a person takes in the face of the reality of which one is a part and / or not. The correct analysis of linguistic production in terms of the functions of communication is the first step to be understood correctly.

Determining the communication functions of language is closely related to Saussure's (2001) language/word opposition. The basis of the word is language. This feature can be explained by its principle of being social and transforming into words with individual use. "Language is a social phenomenon and is based on the need for communication. The most important component of language ability is that human beings can represent beings and objects with signs (Erkman-Akerson, 2007: 40).

Concepts, which are the designs of the beings in the external world reality in the human mind, are represented by language indicators in the world of language. The concept in our minds is the signified, and the syntax consisting of the sounds we embody it is the signifier. The relationship between the signified and the signifier constitutes the language sign. Language is also a structure made up of signs. This structure is the syntax in which lexical morphemes in the language meet with syntactic morphemes and form a whole. The signs in the language gain value with this sequence.

Language, which is a closed system in itself, is a social phenomenon and turns into individual use with the words that individuals create using the signs in the language. The feature that makes language indispensable for society is its use. Just as the internal logics and principles of language are regulated by grammatical rules, the use of language for communication is directed through social rules. These rules are not related to the language itself, but to how it can be used by individuals and are based on common consensus. The individual who speaks/writes and wants to be understood by others must comply with this common agreement (Gökdayı, 2008: 94). In that case, the purpose for which language is used is effective in interpreting and gaining value of the transmitted message. Language gains meaning when it is interpreted according to the purpose determined in the mind of the individual who uses the language. Searle argues that linguistic meaning and communication are not born with random meanings that people attribute to words, but from the unity of words that carry semantic content appropriate to the thoughts and intentions in the mind (Büyükkantarlıođlu, 2006: 47). Every language use has a purpose, and this purpose determines the function of the language. Language takes its meaning from the context in which it is used, that is, language, but some functions are loaded when it is used (Kılıç, 2007: 126). Functions of language refer to the purpose of people to communicate verbally or in writing (Guntermann & Phillips, 1982;

Laine, 1985; Deniz & Çekici, 2019). The purpose of the speaker/producer of the text determines the language uses, and the difference in language usage is parallel to the different functions of the language in the communication process.

Linguists, social scientists, and psychologists have taken different approaches to classify the functions of language. One of these approaches is the classification made by Roman Jakobson from the Prague linguistics circle. Jakobson considers information as basis of communication and states that language has six functions: expression, referent, call, relationship, metalanguage function and artistic function (Jakobson, 1960; Senemoğlu & Vardar, 1999; Huber, 2008; Günay, 2013).

According to Jakobson (1960: 3), language should be studied in all its functions, and this requires a brief examination of the constitutive factors in any speech event/any verbal communication act. The addresser sends a message to addressee. For a message to function, it requires a context to which it is referred, which can be grasped by the recipient, and which can be expressed orally or in writing context; a common code for the addresser and addressee of the message (for the encoder and decoder of the message), and finally, a physical channel and psychological link between the addresser and addressee of the message that allows both to communicate and stay in touch. Jakobson (1960: 3) schematized the elements/factors that are inseparably involved in verbal communication as follows:

Figure 1: Jakobson's communication diagram

Each of these six factors that ensure the realization of the communication performs a separate linguistic function and the linguistic structure of the statement depends on the function that carries weight in that statement (Rifat, 1990: 29; Senemoğlu & Vardar, 1999: 209).

The so-called "emotional" or "expressive" function focuses on the addressee, is aimed at a direct expression of the speaker's attitude towards what she/he is talking about. It tends to create the impression of a certain emotion, whether real or fake (Jakobson, 1960: 4). The expressive function focuses on the speaker is about expressing all kinds of emotions and explaining thoughts. What matters in this function is the presence of the speaker, and the speaker makes this presence felt (Günay, 2013: 398) and evaluates the quality of the referent. The expressive function can be expressed with adjectives, adverbs, exclamation marks, the arrangement of words in the syntax, emphasis, punctuation indicators, or gestures and mimics that have expressive value, in addition to the personal noun I/WE (Kıran and Kıran, 2018: 101).

Recipient orientation, the "conative function" (activation), finds its purest grammatical expression in the call and command that deviates syntactically, morphologically, and often even phonologically from other nouns and verbal categories. (Jakobson, 1960: 4) Since the purpose of this communication is to bring about a response or change in behaviour of the addressee, the conative function defines the relationships between the addresser and

the addressee (Kıran & Kıran, 2018: 104). In the conative function, the use of second person singular or plural pronouns or other linguistic elements that determine these pronouns is dominant (Günay, 2013: 401).

There are messages that primarily serve to establish, prolong, or interrupt communication, to check if the channel is working (Hello, do you hear me?), to attract the attention of the recipient, or to confirm their continued attention. The addresser or addressee using such messages focuses on the channel when they need to check whether they are using the same code (Jakobson, 1960: 5). This channel-oriented function is the "phatic function" that enables the establishment and maintenance of communication between the addresser and the addressee (Kıran & Kıran, 2018: 105).

When it comes to the "poetic function" of language, the key is to use unconventional associations. Unusual associations are one of the most important features of poetic language, and this feature is related to the poetic function, one of the six functions Jakobson has identified (Aksan, 2005: 3). The two essential features inherent in the poetic function are selection and combination. While selection is produced on the basis of equivalence, similarity and difference, synonymy and contrast, the formation and combination of the sequence is based on contiguity. The poetic function reflects the equivalence principle from the axis of choice to the axis of association. At the same time, this function is not the only function of oral art, it is only dominant, determining function and it encourages the sensibility of signs (Jakobson, 1960: 7). On the other hand, the linguistic analysis of the poem cannot be limited only to the poetic function. The features of various poetic genres require the participation of other functions with a certain gradation in parallel with the dominance of the literary function. For example, heroic poetry in the third person often uses the referent function; The first-person lyric poem reflects the function of enthusiasm, the second person poem reflects the conative function (Senemoğlu & Vardar, 1999: 214). The aim of the artistic/poetic function, which focuses on the message itself, is to make the word effective and different with extraordinary reconciliations. For this reason, the poetic function is not only specific to poetry, but includes all kinds of literary texts, but can also be seen in daily language uses, advertising texts and in newspaper.

The "metalingual" function performs the function in which the speaker provides information on the language he or she is using. Discourse focuses on code whenever the speaker and/or recipient deems it necessary to test whether they are using common code. Thus, discourse fulfils a meta-linguistic function (Senemoğlu & Vardar, 1999: 212). Any language learning process, especially children's acquisition of the mother tongue, makes extensive use of such metalinguistic processes (Jakobson, 1960: 6). This function is intended to indicate the meaning of signs that are thought to be incomprehensible to the recipient, in other words, it is the explanation of language with language (Kıran & Kıran, 2018: 110).

Wittgenstein said, "The meaning of a word is its use in the language" (Lyons, 1983: 367) Language, in which the way we perceive the world, and our personal/interpersonal experiences are transformed, and the meanings are shaped by various structures, is a usage. In other words, it is an action, and the system of a language is embodied in the form of text. Thus, the text creates its own context (Halliday & Matthiessen, 2004: 25). The meaning of a literary text is an act that oscillates between its formal expression and its content, which is intended to give all the meanings that the text is supposed to reflect, and it aims to create different concrete values for emotion, excitement, enthusiasm, or the human spirit (Günay, 2013). Different types of texts address different functions of language. Selecting and combining actions in the text are performed according to the determined linguistic function. For this reason, for linguistic communication to take place in a healthy way, the produced message/text must be correctly analysed/understood in terms of the functions of the language. This is an act of discovery, constructing meaning, and this skill should be structured in individuals from an early age. However, although the achievements determined at each grade level in the Turkish Language Curriculum (MEB, 2019) are presented to the students through texts, there is no gain for teaching the functions of the language in the program. The absence of an explanation stating that the program was prepared on the basis of functional language education and the absence of any function list also indicates that it was not prepared according to functional language education (Deniz & Demir, 2021: 40). According to the high school Turkish Language and Literature Curriculum (MEB, 2018), activities related to the acquisition in the field of Oral Communication stated as "*Communication and its elements are explained, their functions are emphasized*" are organized in the 9th grade

textbooks. In the Turkish Language Teaching undergraduate program, Roman Jakobson, one of the theorists who adopted the Structuralist approach, and his classification of the functions of the language were included in the content of the Linguistics course given in the fifth semester. Through this course, Turkish teacher candidates are expected to have the ability to analyse literary texts in terms of language functions. The knowledge of the subject will turn into the ability of students to consider the texts in terms of the dominant function used and to determine their type and/or to write different texts of the same type. Acquiring the achievements of understanding, analysing, interpreting texts, teaching genre knowledge and subjective/objective judgments in the Turkish Language Curriculum (2019) also depends on the assimilation of knowledge about the functions of language. Raising awareness in this direction is, of course, possible if Turkish teachers can know and correctly use the communicative functions of the language. The aim of this study is to examine the sentence-level linguistic units used by Turkish teacher candidates in narrative texts in terms of functions of the language by using Jakobson's approach and to determine the diversity of using functions.

2. Method

2.1. Research Design

The research is qualitative research based on the case study. In the research, this method was chosen because it was aimed to reveal the situations in which the pre-service teachers could use the functions of the language in the narrative texts they wrote before and after learning the subject related to the functions of the language within the scope of general linguistics course.

Case study is a system whose boundaries can be defined. In qualitative research, in which the researcher reveals one or more situations in detail (Christen, Johnson & Turner, 2015), collecting information about one or more individuals, groups, institutions, societies or a specific phenomenon, situation or event, in-depth examination. The studies that aim to make and provide rich explanatory information (Davey, 1990; Merriam, 2013; Yin, 2017; Kaleli Yılmaz, 2019) are case studies. Definiteness, descriptiveness, and intuitivism are explained as the most important features of case study (Merriam, 2013). In line with these features, the research was based on the examination of the products obtained before and after the learned subject, the products were tried to be described in terms of the use of the functions of the language and these limits were not exceeded. The data obtained were analysed based on the literature and the results were systematically presented.

2.2. Study Group

While forming the study group of the research, convenient sampling (Merriam, 2013), one of the purposive sampling methods, was used. The participants in the study are 33 second-year students studying in the department of Turkish education at the faculty of education of a state university and taking the general linguistics course. All the participants were recruited from among the volunteers without considering their demographic characteristics.

2.3. Data Collection

The data of the research is based on the document analysis method. One of the many methods used to collect data in case studies is document review. In cases where it is not possible to collect data through direct observation and interview in qualitative research, the documents provide a rich data source and provide information to the researcher about many unobservable situations (Patton, 2014: 293). Within the scope of the study, participants have written a narrative text with the theme of "This city and me" without explaining the subject of "Functions of Language". The narration of a plot by the narrator with a certain point of view in a certain time frame and in a certain sequence order are important features that make a text narrative (Günay, 2013: 137). In other words, different functions of language can be included due to features such as the sequence of events and situations in the narrative in time and the interaction of the narrators with each other. At the same time, clauses stand out in surface structures, as narrative texts carry cause, effect, intention, goal attainment and time relations. This feature enables the use of different functions of language throughout the narrative

(Dilidüzgün, 2017: 99). Considering the usability of different functions of language in narrative texts, the participants were asked to write a narrative text in the research. According to the content of the linguistics course, participants examined and discussed the six functions of language in the communication process defined by Roman Jakobson from the Prague Linguistics circle. In the following week, various examples of the functions of language were presented and practices were carried out in the form of determining the functions in the texts given with the participants / writing different examples suitable for the functions. Two weeks after the exercise, the participants wrote a narrative text again on the same theme. The first and second narrative texts written were analysed and evaluated in terms of language functions, using Jakobson's approach, and the use of language functions in the narrative texts of the participants was identified.

2.4. Data Analysis

Case study analysis requires an in-depth description of the situation under investigation (Creswell, 2015: 199). The data of the research were analysed according to the descriptive analysis approach, as they were interpreted according to the themes that were previously created in the literature and direct quotations were made while writing the results. The purpose of descriptive analysis is to present the findings to the reader in an organized and interpreted form (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2013: 256).

While analysing the data of the research, the narrative texts of the participants were named as representative, the first texts were given codes as “K1a, K2a, K3a...” and the second texts as “K1b, K2b, K3b...”. In the determination of the functions in the narrative texts, units at the sentence level were chosen. Speech-action theory was considered in the selection of sentences as the unit of analysis. According to the speech-action theory, the speaker/sender produces separate sentences when s/he wants to convey his intention to the listener/receiver. The utterance, which is the basic unit of speech-action theory, is a sentence said by a certain person at a certain time and space (Kılıç, 2007: 127). The sentence is the basic unit of the text. The discourses in the narratives, which are directly transferred using colons and quotation marks, and the indirect transfers in which the discourse is presented not as it is, but by transferring it into an utterance (Korkut, 2017: 124) were also accepted as a sentence and examined in terms of the functions of the language. It would not be correct to say that only one function of the language is used in any linguistic unit. Functions co-exist and each can participate in a sentence to varying degrees. Multiple functions of the language can be used in a sentence, but one function is dominant over the others depending on the type of communication and/or the speaker's intention (Kılıç, 2007; Kıran & Kıran, 2018). For this reason, the point of view of the narrative text was taken as a basis in marking the dominant functions in the sentences, and attention was paid to how the narrator positions self throughout the narrative.

The coding made to ensure the validity of the research was checked by a field expert other than the researcher. In addition, direct quotations from the narrative texts of the participants in the study group (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2013) were included in the data analysis process. In terms of the reliability of the research, the consistency between the coders was checked. 40 sentences selected from the data were coded in terms of dominant function by a field expert other than the researcher. Miles and Huberman's (2015) reliability formula as $\text{Reliability} = \frac{\text{Number of consensus}}{\text{Total agreement} + \text{Number of disagreements}}$ was used for the percentage of agreement of the coders. It was concluded that the coders reached a consensus of .87 percent.

3. Results

The first and second texts of the participants were examined in terms of the functions of the language and the number of sentences that included all functions as the dominant function is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Number of Dominant Functions Used by Pre-Service Teachers in the First And Second Narrative Texts

Participant	Text	Referential Function	Expressive Function	Conative Function	Phatic Function	Poetic Function	Metalinguistic Function
		<i>f</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>f</i>
K1	First	4	9	-	-	6	-

	Second	25	16	1	1	7	-
K2	First	56	61	10	4	3	-
	Second	66	47	11	8	5	-
K3	First	32	3	7	-	-	-
	Second	55	7	11	4	-	-
K4	First	28	3	-	-	7	-
	Second	27	4	1	3	6	-
K5	First	11	3	3	-	-	-
	Second	15	3	3	2	-	1
K6	First	34	5	3	3	-	-
	Second	24	5	10	5	3	1
K7	First	32	-	-	-	2	-
	Second	30	1	-	2	2	1
K8	First	53	6	3	7	3	-
	Second	60	4	-	6	4	-
K9	First	74	7	10	8	5	-
	Second	48	15	10	5	6	-
K10	First	35	7	4	7	1	-
	Second	32	9	7	5	1	-
K11	First	24	6	3	-	-	-
	Second	21	7	6	3	-	-
K12	First	24	-	-	-	1	-
	Second	31	3	1	3	-	-
K13	First	29	-	-	1	-	-
	Second	27	-	2	2	-	-
K14	First	35	3	-	3	2	-
	Second	42	4	1	5	2	-
K15	First	102	5	3	10	4	1
	Second	104	15	6	7	2	2
K16	First	50	-	1	1	3	-
	Second	52	7	6	3	3	-
K17	First	109	11	6	10	3	-
	Second	108	12	5	11	3	-
K18	First	17	22	11	-	26	-
	Second	15	22	12	-	30	-
K19	First	72	7	4	9	4	-
	Second	42	-	4	6	1	-
K20	First	70	9	3	1	4	-
	Second	21	1	1	1	4	-
K21	First	37	2	1	2	-	-
	Second	39	-	2	1	-	-
K22	First	31	-	4	-	2	-
	Second	23	-	4	1	5	-
K23	First	20	-	-	-	4	-
	Second	25	2	7	4	-	-
K24	First	2	-	1	-	14	-
	Second	6	1	2	-	11	-
K25	First	48	-	2	1	-	-
	Second	62	5	5	3	-	-
K26	First	47	9	7	5	1	-
	Second	47	9	8	4	1	-
K27	First	82	29	17	13	7	-
	Second	82	34	16	17	7	-
K28	First	30	7	2	2	-	-
	Second	34	4	5	4	-	-
K29	First	76	-	-	-	2	-
	Second	76	-	-	-	2	-
K30	First	21	-	10	-	2	-

	Second	22	5	8	1	3	-
K31	First	37	-	5	5	-	-
	Second	33	1	2	3	-	-
K32	First	38	4	3	2	-	-
	Second	36	8	3	1	1	-
K33	First	25	-	-	-	2	-
	Second	23	-	-	-	2	-

In Table 1, the number of functions used by the participants in their first and second texts is given separately. In how many sentences the functions are used as dominant functions, they are presented one by one according to the first and second texts. The referent function was mostly used in the second texts of the participants coded K1, K2, K3, K5, K8, K12, K14, K15, K16, K21, K23, K24, K25, K28 and K30. The number of sentences in which K1 coded participle referential function is dominant changes from 4 to 25, K2 from 56 to 66, K3 from 32 to 55, K8 from 53 to 60, K12 from 24 to 31, K14 35 from ' to 42, K25 from 48 to 62. For example, participant K1 inserted another narrative into his second text. Sentences with referential functions are more intense in this inner narrative, which is conveyed from an observer's point of view.

K1b. *In one of the countries, there was a palace with all kinds of plants in it and a huge pool in the middle. A beautiful girl lived in this palace. One day, she got very bored and went out of the palace and started to wander.*

...

Sentences with referential functions were used more in the second text of the participant coded K2, which included more details than the first text.

K2b. ... *Splashing mud and branches hitting my face, a hut appeared. A very small hut with only one room, with three walls. One wall is missing. There was a child inside, a lonely child. The woman came to the boy, gave him the bread, and then kissed him. The boy took the bread and began to eat it. ...*

Participants with the codes K4, K6, K7, K9, K10, K11, K13, K17, K18, K19, K20, K22, K31, K32, K33 decreased the number of sentences in which the referent function was dominant in their second text. The participant coded K6 reduced this number from 34 to 24, K9 from 74 to 48, K19 from 72 to 42, K20 from 70 to 21, and K22 from 31 to 23. In the second texts of K4, K6, K9, K10 and K22, the number of sentences in which other functions are dominant has increased. This situation can be considered as the reason why the referent function is used less. The following part, taken from both texts of participant K22, shows that he tends to use different functions in the second text:

K22a. *"One morning, while opening his shop, he saw a man lying in front of the shutters. It was a ragged beggar covered in a scraggle. Beyzi, enraged by the sight she encountered, said, "What are you doing here?" The beggar walked away without saying anything, feeling the coldness of the air in his entire being, with just an innocent smile. Beyzi opened his shop after the man left and began to sweep in front of his. His customer closed his shop after a day and went home under heavy blizzard.* (First text)

K22b. *"One day, once again, he saw a man lying down on the icy cobblestones as if to say 'not to care' while he was lifting the shutters, supposedly to serve people. The wrinkled face, his clothes torn to pieces, the wretched man was nothing more than a beggar. Beyzi angrily said to him, "What are you doing here? Get out of here quickly!" said. The man walked away with only an innocent smile on his face. After the man left, Beyzi opened his shop and started to clean the front. After a day without customers, he closed his shop and set off with the aim of reaching his home by getting lost among the misty streets as they reached the earth with a rhythm resembling the rhythm of snowflakes* (second text)

In both texts of participants with codes K26, K27 and K29, the number of sentences in which the referent function is dominant is equal.

Findings related to expressiveness function, In the second texts of participants coded K1, P3, K4, K7, K9, K10, K11, K12, K14, K15, K16, K17, K23, K24, K25, K27, K30, K31 and K32, presented increased number of sentences with expressive function. The participant with the code K1 increased this number from 9 to 16, K9 from 7 to 15, K12 from 24 to 31, K15 from 5 to 15, and K16 from 0 to 7. For example, participant K15 preferred the observer point of view in his/her first text, and the narrator is "I" in the second text. This choice has increased the use of the expressiveness function in the second text.

K15a. she was in two minds and unsettle. *Was this the person he wanted to be, didn't he believe in things, or did he ignore them? Everyone in the minibus seemed to know what he was going through. He started to get bored. loosened his tie. He didn't like minibuses since they started working anyway. ...* (first text)

K15b.

I was so bored; I couldn't calm down. I was trying to name my feelings. Was this the person I wanted to be, weren't the things I believed in or was I ignoring them? It was as if everyone in the minibus knew what I was going through. I am getting bored. I loosened my tie. I didn't like the minibus since I started working anyway. ... (second text)

Participants with the codes K2, K8, K20 and K28 included less expressive sentences in their second texts. While the participants coded K19 and K21 used the expressive function in their first texts, they did not use it in their second texts. The participant coded K21 directly conveyed the narratives of the narrators in the "I" language in her first text, and in the second text the participant translated these narratives into indirect transmission.

K21a. ... *He went to the President's office. She greeted him very cordially at the door. They got right to the point. "We're asking you for a mission that we haven't asked for before. We don't know how ready you are for this." ...* (first text)

Participants K13, K22, K29, K33 never used the expressive function in both their first and second texts. In both texts of P5 (3), P6 (5), P18 (22) and K26 (9) participants, the number of sentences in which dominant expressive function is equal. The number in parentheses next to the participant codes is the number of sentences used in this function. In the first text of the participant coded K18, the narrator is "we" and in the second text, it is "me". The narrator intensely reflects his emotions. For this reason, there are many sentences in which the expressive function and the poetic function are dominant.

K18a. *Without considering the depth of the lines drawn on our faces, we watch the smiles trying to show themselves under the drooping cheeks. Deep inside we are forced to step into the leaves of the past. Then the smell of hungover darkness falls on us. Like our secrets that we cannot carry, we breathe at night without losing our sincerity. ...* (first text)

K18b. *Without considering the depth of the lines drawn on our faces, we watch the smiles trying to show themselves under the drooping cheeks. I find it hard inside to step into the leaves of the past. Then the smell of hungover darkness falls on me. Like our secrets that we cannot carry, I breathe at night without losing my sincerity. Although I want some happiness alongside the sadness, I feel the empty heart like a piece of paper stuck in my hand....* (Second text)

Findings regarding the conative function revealed the number of sentences with a conative function in the second texts of the participants coded K1, K2, K3, K4, K6, K10, K11, K12, K13, K14, K15, K16, K18, K21, K23, K24, K25, K26 and K28. shows an increase. The participant coded K3 increased the number of sentences in which the conative function was dominant from 7 to 11, K6 from 3 to 10, and K16 from 1 to 6. While the participant K23 did not use the conative function in first text, compared to 7 sentences in the second text. It can be said that the increase in the number of sentences with a conative function in the second texts is related to the direct transfers of the participants from the narrators.

K16a. ... *After they both left the classroom and walked for a while, the principal took Semih aside and said that he received a phone call, that his mother was sick and that he was in intensive care.* (First text)

K16b. ... *Suddenly, the door of the classroom opened more hastily than ever before. It was the principal who entered. The principal said in a worried tone:*

- *Semih, come with me quickly. We need to talk.*

After they both left the classroom and walked for a while, the principal pulled Semih aside.

- *Semih, I have something to tell you now, but please do not worry. I just got a call from the hospital. ...* (second text)

K23a. ... *The old man perched on the side of the curb, thinking that he had already exhausted his strength to climb the hill at that moment. From where he was sitting, he started to watch the afternoon rush of the people in the neighbourhood on the one hand, and the last few minutes of pleasure efforts of the children, who were covered in sweat, from their games, on the other. Then he remembered the childhood he spent on these streets. ...* (first text)

K23b. ... *He sat down on the curb, thinking he needed some strength to climb this hill today. At that time, one of the children on the street said to his friend, "Ahmet, we are waiting for you. Come out!" he called. The old man thought about his childhood years. He used to run and play in these streets seventy years ago...* (second text)

The number of sentences in which the conative function is dominant in the second texts of the participants coded K17, K27, K30 and K31 is less than in the first texts. The participant K8 used the covenant function in 3 sentences in the first text but did not include this function in the second text.

Participants with the codes K5 (3), K9 (10), K19 (4), K22 (4) and K32 (3) use the conative function in both texts equally, while participants with the codes K7, K29 and K33 did not include the conative function in both their first and second texts.

According to the findings related to the phatic function, the participants with the codes K1, C2, K3, K4, K5, K6, K7, K11, K12, K13, K14, K16, K17, K22, K23, K25, K27, K28 and K30 used the phatic function more in their second texts. The P2 coded participant increased the number of sentences in which the phatic function was dominant from 4 to 8, K23 from 0 to 4, and P27 from 13 to 17.

K27a. ... *"You will not prove me right and go, and I will not be able to get used to a happy life without you." he said, pulling the door, giving concreteness to his desire to let himself out. He quickly went down the stairs ...* (first text)

K27b. ... *"You will not prove me right and go, and I will not be able to get used to a happy life without you. he said, pulling the door, giving concreteness to his desire to let himself out. Goodbye." He could say. Would the woman be able to say goodbye? He hurried down the stairs...* (second text)

Participants coded K8, K9, K10, K15, K19, K21, K26, K31 and K32 used the phatic function more in their first texts. Participants K18, K24, K29, K33 never used the phatic function in both their first and second texts. The participant coded K20 included this function in only one sentence in both texts.

Findings regarding the poetic function show that the number of sentences in which this function is dominant in the second texts of the participants with the codes K1, C2, K6, K8, K9, K18, K22, K30 and K32 increased. K6 increased the number of sentences from 0 to 3, K18 from 26 to 30, K22 from 2 to 5.

K18b. ... *"Will the accumulated summers melt the winters in the last moments of the ignited fire? While the whites are burning in our bodies, on the last day they will seek our ashes in a handful. Take a good look at those palms, the picture that will come to your mind as you look, will you?*

I'm looking into your eyes, / Without hearing hell. / I'm listening to your words, / without knowing your smell / My pages are dusty now / from not being able to tell / my whites are black / My visible mountains are snowy / like sky / you too ... (second text)

Participants with the codes K15, K19 and K24 included more in the sentence in which the poetic function was dominant in their first texts. The participant K12 used the poetic function in 1 sentence in the first text, and the participant K23 used the poetic function in 4 sentences. These participants did not include any poetic function in their second texts.

K24a. *lonely and tired sea... He looks at the sky like his hand is with a whip. Weak birds fly in the sky. The sky is pale, the sky is helpless, the sky is lonely today. The sea is watching with the greatest pain that a hijra can give.* ... (first text)

Coded K7 (2), K10 (1), K14 (2), K16 (3), K17 (3), K20 (4), K26 (1), K27 (7), K29 (2), K33 (2) participants used the poetic function in an equal number of sentences in their first and second texts. On the other hand, participants coded K3, K5, K11, K13, K21, K25, K28 and K31 did not use the artistic function in both texts.

The metalanguage function is one that is almost never included in the texts of the participants. It can be said that the reason for this situation is closely related to the fact that the texts are narrative texts. The participant coded K15 used the metalanguage function in a sentence in the first text.

Participants with the codes K5, P6, K7 used the metalanguage function in 1 sentence in their second text, and the participant with the code K15 in 2 sentences. Other participants did not include this function in both their first and second texts.

K6a. ... *"My dear children, do not play with coyotes, they are not your kind. Besides, they're very cunning. The baby parrot said, "Mother, what do you mean it's not your kind?" she asked. "Not the same sex as us, meaning no parrot, no bird, baby" ...* (second text)

K7b. ... These robots surrounded the world like a swarm of locusts.

A robot is a machine that cleans, looks at its dirty basket without programming what to do, washes the laundry if it is full, does the ironing, cooks if the pot is empty, and waters the flowers... (second text)

K15b. ... *I woke up from the dream as the statues around me were coming towards me. It was dawn time. It is the time between predawn and sunrise. I washed my hands and my face. I remembered what the boy said...*
(second text)

When we look at the use of functions in the narrative texts written by the pre-service teachers before and after learning the subject about the functions of the language, it is seen that the functions are used more in the second texts. The findings regarding the issue are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Frequency and Percentage Analysis of Functions Used by Pre-service Teachers in Their First and Second Texts

Functions of language	First text		Second text	
	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%
Referential	1385	71,7	1353	67,6
Expressiveness	218	11,3	251	12,5
Conative	123	6,3	160	7,9
Phatic	94	4,8	121	6
Poetic	108	5,5	111	5,5
Metalanguage	1	0,05	5	0,24
	1929		2001	

The number of sentences in which the dominant function was examined in the participants' first texts was 1929. Looking at the functions one by one, the referential function is used as the dominant function in 71.7%, the expressive function in 11.3%, the Conative function in 6.3%, the phatic function in 4.8%, the poetic function in 5.5%, and the metalanguage function in only 1 sentence. The number of sentences in which the dominant function was examined in the second texts of the participants was 2001. In this issue, the referent function was used as 67.6%, the expressive function 12.5%, the conative function 7.9%, the phatic function 6%, the poetic function 5.5%, and the metalanguage function was used as the dominant function in 5 sentences. When we look at the usage rate of functions in the first and second texts, there is a decrease in the use of the referent function and an increase in the use of other functions.

4. Discussion

In the study, in which the narrative texts written by 33 Turkish teacher candidates before and after teaching the functions of language were examined in terms of their ability to use the functions, it was concluded that the referent function was used less in the second texts, while the use of other functions increased in the second texts. The results regarding the use of functions in the first and second texts are as follows:

1. The number of sentences with referential function increased in the second text of 15 participants compared to the first text. In the first text of 15 participants, the number of sentences in which the referent function is dominant is high. 3 participants used an equal number of referential sentences in their first and second texts. The act of language is performed in the context of a discourse and only gains meaning in this context (Syal, 2018: 59). In the sentences in which the referent function is dominant, not the reality of the external world, but the context of the text in which the external world is represented and the interlinguistic referent is taken into consideration. According to A. J. Greimas, intralinguistic referent is the language elements that the discourse is based on, that it creates within itself, that has no referent in the outside world, that creates a referent in the discourse (Kıran & Kıran, 2007: 113). A written, completed text is a concrete object and forms a self-enclosed whole (Uçan, 2006: 44). At the same time, in such texts, language creates its own content or referent with a unique arrangement. It does not always have to be directed towards a referent in the non-linguistic world (Göktürk, 1986: 27). For this reason, it is possible to say that the referent function is intense in the first and second texts of the participants compared to other functions.

The type of text can often be regarded as a feature that determines which linguistic function will be used predominantly. In this research, the participants were asked to write a narrative text, considering that different functions of language could be used. The texts have not been analysed in terms of narrator and point of view, but it is seen that these concepts have an effect especially in the use of referential and expressive functions. The narrator and the narrated are the people who take place in the language and find their existence in the context of the text. The narrator's way of telling the events also explains his way of seeing, and the reader perceives the events in the narrative with the narrator's way of seeing. When the narration is told using the third person singular, the narrator speaks of the narrator as "he-she" (Günay, 2013: 142). The narrative is presented by an observer when the point of view is someone other than the characters of the narrative. The use of language by this narrator is a reference to the context in the narrative, as it conveys the events in an impartial way (Günay, 2013: 145). This use of language, in which the narrator does not state his own feelings, intentions, and ideas, is also closely related to the referential function. It is thought that the use of language determined by the preferred point of view is a reason why the referent function is used more than other functions in both the first and second texts.

The results regarding the use of functions in the first and second texts in terms of the general participants show that the referent function is used less in the second texts than in the first texts. It can be argued that the use of the referent function has decreased in parallel with the increase in the use of other functions of the language in the second texts.

2. The expressiveness function was used more in the second text of 19 participants than in the first texts. On the other hand, five participants reduced the expressiveness function in their second text. Four participants never used this function in their second text. Two participants used the expressive function in their first text, but not in their second text. When the narrator is one of the heroes of the narrative and tells a story about himself according to his position in the event, tells about the events that he has gone through, or tells everything from his own point of view, instead of conveying the conversations of other people in the narrative indirectly, when he leaves the word to the protagonist speaking at that time, the first person pronoun "I" is used (Günay, 2013: 142; Ögeyik, 2006: 119). utterances called "I" language with a psychological approach, are speaker/sender oriented. In speaker/sender-oriented discourses, the expressiveness function affects the syntax and utterances in which the speaker is the subject are produced (Börekçi & Ekinci Çelikpazu, 2011). This feature draws attention in the sentences in which the "I" language is used in the first and second texts of the participants and therefore the expressive function is dominant. In terms of the functions, the results show that the use of the expressiveness function increases in the second texts compared to the first texts. It is seen that one of the reasons for the increase in the expressiveness function in some of the second texts is related to the narrator and his point of view. The language use shaped by the perspective of the external narrative narrator preferred in the first text left its place to the language use of the internal narrative narrator in the second text.

3. The conative function was used more in the second text of 19 participants than in the first texts. In the second text of six participants, the use of the conative function decreased. Five participants used the conative function in an equal number of sentences in their first and second texts, and three participants never used this function in both their first and second texts. One participant used the conative function in the first text, but not in the second text. The results of the general use of functions in the first and second texts show that the conative function is used more in the second texts than in the first texts. There is a case of calling out in sentences in which the conative function is dominant, which drags the receiver to an act or behaviour (Dilidüzgün, 2017: 45). In this way, the speaker used language that attracts the attention of the receiver and prompts him to perform an activity/behaviour in this usage, the "you/you" discourse is prominent. It is possible to talk about the effect speech act, especially in sentences where the conative function is dominant. In the effect speech act, the speaker invites the receiver to think with an inquiry, forces them to think or asks them to act (Günay, 2013: 401). Participants generally preferred the conative function in such sentences, where it aims to make an impact on the person being called.

4. As with the conative function, the phatic function was used more frequently in the second text of 19 participants. In the second text of nine participants, the use of this function decreased. Four participants never

used the relation function in both texts. One participant used it once in both texts. Malinowski points out that the sole or primary function of many of our utterances is not to convey information, to give orders, to convey hopes, wishes or wishes, or to express feelings, but to establish and maintain social solidarity. In certain contexts, the socially determined "Hello, how are you?" such utterances fulfil the phatic function. Mobility in speech is linked to other utterances based on relational utterances (Lyons, 1983: 373). The use of the phatic function in narrative texts is aimed at establishing, prolonging/sustaining/not interrupting communication, and keeping communication channels open (Mera, 2017: 37). It was concluded that the use of this function for the stated purposes increased in the participants' second texts.

5. The use of poetic function increased in the second text of nine participants. In the second text of three participants, the use of this function has decreased. Two participants used the poetic function in the first text but did not include it in the second text. Ten participants included a poetic function in an equal number of sentences in both texts. Eight participants did not use this function in both their first and second texts. Overall, the results show that the usage rate of the poetic function is equal in terms of the first and second texts. In the poetic function, language indicators function as a stimulus that creates various designs, images, associations, and different emotions (İşeri & Demirgüneş, 2008: 502), and describe the aesthetic function based on the effect (Bati, 2007: 3). In their narratives, the participants included unusual associations in which the aesthetic function was dominant/intense. Particularly, both the first and the second text of the participant coded K18 exhibit the feature of "rhetorical text in which the expression style that aims to create emotional intensity by appealing to the spiritual side of the person is preferred" (Günay, 2013: 291). These language uses, in which the enunciation subject's actions turn into linguistic metaphorical structures (Lakoff & Johnson, 2015), focus on how he says rather than what he says, and these language uses with intense different images, have an impact on the receiver and draw attention to the intensity of the targeted emotional state. The poetic function for the message itself is realized by giving importance to the inner worlds, feelings, principles, and dramas of the heroes in the narrative texts (Mera, 2017: 41).

6. Among the functions, the most limited one in terms of its use in the narrative text is the metalanguage function. This function was used one time by only one participant in the first texts. Four participants used the metalanguage function in their second text, 28 participants did not use it in both texts. The results of the general use of the metalanguage function in terms of the first and second texts show that the use of this function in the second texts has increased. The meta-language function, which we can encounter especially in the instructional texts, was used in the second narrative texts of the participants.

The results of the study showed that pre-service teachers were able to transform their knowledge of Jakobson's Classification of Language Functions into conscious use skills in the second narrative texts they wrote. Six functions in Jakobson's (1960) classification of the functions of language in the communication process are an integral part of a literary text. The type of text, the purpose of writing, the preferred narrator and point of view determine which function will be used dominantly in that text. Especially in narrative texts, functions are used together. Mera (2017), in her research in which she analysed the poem "Milasao's Songs" introduced in high school textbooks in terms of functions of language, drew attention to the intertwined use of functions. The results of this research confirm the same fact.

References

- Aksan, D. (2005). The language of poetry. *Journal of Language and Literature*, 2(1), 1-13. <http://ded.mersindilbilim.info/tr/pub/issue/19505/207828>
- Bati, U. (2007). The usage of rhetorical tropes in advertisements. *Öneri Journal*, 7(28), 327-35. <https://doi.org/10.14783/maruoneri.684446>
- Börekçi, M. & Ekinci Çelikpazu, E. (2011, November 16-18). *The Divan of İbrahim Hakki in terms of Poetic Discourse*[Conference presentation]. Erzurumlu İbrahim Hakki Symposium in All Its Aspects. Erzurum.
- Börekçi, M. (2009). *Words in terms of structure and function in Turkey Turkish*. Erzurum: Eser Ofset.
- Büyükkantarçioğlu, N. (2006). *Social reality and language*. İstanbul: Multilingual.

- Christensen, L. B., Johnson, R. B., & Turner, L. A. (2015). *Research methods: Design and analysis* (2nd Edition). Ankara: Anı Publishing.
- Creswell, J. W. (2015). *Qualitative research methods*. M. Tüm, S. B. Demir (Trans. Eds.). Ankara: Siyasal Bookstore.
- Davey, L. (1990). The application of case study evaluations. *Practical Assessment, Research and Evaluation*, 2(1), 9. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.7275/02g8-bb93>
- Deniz, K. & Çekici Y. E. (2019). An analysis of the “Türkçe öğreniyorum” course book in terms of the language functions. *Turkish Studies Educational Sciences*, 14(6), 3043-3062. DOI: 10.29228/TurkishStudies.39410
- Deniz, K. & Demir, E. (2021). Language functions in the objectives of the Turkish language teaching program. *Avrasya Dil Eğitimi ve Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 5(1), 23-46. <http://dergipark.gov.tr/ader>
- Dilidüzgün, Ş. (2017). *Text linguistics and Turkish language teaching*. Ankara: Anı Publishing.
- Erkman-Akerson, F. (2007). *An overview of the language with Turkish examples*. İstanbul: Multilingual.
- Gökdayı, H. (2008). True and false in the evaluation of language use. *Erdem*, 51, 91-109. <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/pub/erdem/issue/43876/539917>
- Göktürk, A. (1986). *Translation: The language of languages*. İstanbul: Çağdaş Publications.
- Guntermann, G. & Phillips, J. K. (1982). *Functional- notional concepts: Adapting the foreign language textbook*. U.S.A: The Center for Applied Linguistics Washington.
- Günay, D. (2013). *Text information* (4th Edition). İstanbul: Papatya.
- Halliday, M. A. K. & Matthiessen, C. (2004). *An introduction to functional grammar*. London: Hodder Arnold.
- Huber, E. (2008). *Introduction to linguistics*. İstanbul: Multilingual.
- İşeri, K. & Demirgüneş, S. (2008). The semantical/semiotical analysis of the poem named “Sessiz Gemi”. *Turkish Studies*, 3(4), 499-513. DOI:<http://dx.doi.org/10.7827/TurkishStudies.375>
- Jakobson, R. (1960). Linguistics and Poetics. T. Sebeok (Ed.), *Style in language* (pp. 350-377). Cambridge: Massachusetts Institute of Technology Press. https://pure.mpg.de/rest/items/item_2350615_3/component/file_2350614/content
- Kaleli Yılmaz, G. (2019). The exception handling method. H. Özmen, O. Karamustafaoğlu (Eds.), *Research methods in education* (pp. 251-274). Ankara: Pegem Publishing.
- Kılıç, V. (2007). Functions of language: text-act theory approach. *Journal of Social Sciences*, 1(02), 124-138. <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/download/article-file/43884>
- Kıran, Z. & Eziler Kıran, A. (2018). *Introduction to linguistics* (5th Edition). Ankara: Seçkin Publications.
- Kıran, Z. & Kıran, A. (2007). *Literary reading processes*. Ankara: Seçkin Publishing.
- Korkut, E. (2017). *Word and identity*. Ankara: Seçkin Publishing.
- Laine, E. (1985). *The notional-functional approach: Teaching the real language in its natural context*. Master's Thesis of Arts French, George Mason University, Virginia.
- Lakoff, G. & Johnson, M. (2015). *Metaphors* (Translated by Gökhan Yavuz Demir). İstanbul: İthaki.
- Lyons, J. (1983). *Introduction to theoretical linguistics* (Turkish: A. Kocaman). Ankara: Turkish Language Association Publications.
- Mera, R. (2017). Communicative functions of Girolamo de Rada's literary work treated in the high school textbook "the Albanian language and literature. *Journal Association 1901 "SEPIKE"*, 35-41.
- Merriam, S. B. (2013). *A guide to qualitative research, design and practice*. S. Turan (Trans. Ed.). Ankara: Nobel Publications.
- Miles, M. B. and Huberman, A. M. (2015). *Qualitative data analysis*. (Translation from the 2nd edition). S. Akbaba Altun, A. Ersoy (Eds.). Ankara: Pegem Academy.
- Millî Eğitim Bakanlığı. (2018). *Secondary education Turkish language and literature course 9th, 10th, 11th and 12th grades curriculum*. Ankara: Ministry of National Education Publications.
- Millî Eğitim Bakanlığı. (2019). *Primary education Turkish course curriculum (1-8th grades)*. Ankara: Ministry of National Education Publications.
- Ögeyik, M. C. (2006). Narrative communication and ambiguity. C. Yıldız & L. Beyreli (Eds.), *Linguistics, language teaching and translation studies* (pp. 117-124). Ankara: PegemA Publishing.
- Patton, M. Q. (2014). *Qualitative research and evaluation methods*. M. Tüm, S. B. Demir (Trans. Eds.). Ankara: Pegem Academy.
- Rifat, M. (1990). *Contemporary theories of linguistics and semiotics* (1st Edition). Düzlem Publications.
- Saussure, F. (2001). *General linguistics courses* (Translated by B. Vardar). İstanbul: Multilingual.
- Senemoğlu, O. & Vardar, B. (1999). Roman Jakobson. *Twentieth Century Linguistics* (pp. 201-220). İstanbul: Multilingual.
- Syal, P. (2018). Landmark the study of language and style in literature: An overview. *Language and Language Teaching*, 7(1), 58-63.
- Uçan, H. (2006). *Literary criticism and semiotics*. Ankara: Hece Publications.
- Yıldırım, A., Şimşek, H. (2013). *Qualitative research methods in the social sciences*. Ankara: Seçkin Publishing.

- Yin, R. K. (2017). *Case study research applications* (Translation from 3rd Edition: Prof. Dr. İlhan Günbayı). Ankara: Nobel Academic Publishing.
- Yücel, E. (2009). Speech act in everyday life. *Journal of Selcuk University Institute of Social Sciences*, 21, 515-518. <https://dergipark.org.tr/en/pub/susbed/issue/61797/924437>